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HBIM parametric modeling of Metropolitan Cathedral of Brazilian

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Abstract: The process of documenting and recording historical artifacts presents a significant challenge. Among the primary methods of data acquisition are point clouds derived from digital scanning and, where feasible, existing documents, architectural plans, and archival records. This study proposes a comprehensive workflow for the modeling of the Metropolitan Cathedral of Brasília through the development of a parametric HBIM (Heritage Building Information Modeling) object within a BIM (Building Information Modeling) environment. The initial stage involves the use of digitized original plans and 2D CAD drawings consisting solely of basic geometric entities such as lines, arcs, and circles, which are now translated into a BIM context through parametric modeling and visual programming techniques. The relevance of the research lies in the diverse and multifaceted applications that BIM tools and methodologies offer to the field of heritage conservation. These applications encompass static and dynamic structural analyses informed by the model's geometric data, comprehensive documentation, inventory management, restoration and preservation planning, maintenance strategies, and the implementation of damage assessment and retrofitting methodologies.

Keywords: Historical Building Information Modeling, BIM model, Heritage, Dynamo

1. Introduction

The preservation and conservation of heritage structures inherently demand a multidisciplinary approach, engaging professionals from engineering, architecture, and archaeology. A critical component of this process is the systematic documentation of the asset, which serves as a foundation for informed decision-making in future interventions. This documentation encompasses a wide range of data, including geometric configurations, material properties, degradation patterns, records of past interventions, and structural damage.

Despite its importance, the integration and management of such heterogeneous data remains a persistent challenge. Factors contributing to this difficulty include the absence or inaccessibility of documentation, the fragmented nature of available information, and the lack of digital standardization. Even when digital formats are available, data is frequently non-interoperable—often due to a lack of semantic structure or meaningful interconnectivity—thereby impeding cohesive analysis and multidisciplinary collaboration (Arayici, 2008).

Within this context, the application of Building Information Modeling to heritage assets—commonly referred to as Historic Building Information Modeling (HBIM) — emerges as a valuable tool for supporting long-term documentation efforts. Heritage-related information spans a broad spectrum, encompassing geometric configurations, material specifications, records of restorations and interventions, as well as structural pathologies. The adoption of BIM methodology in heritage contexts facilitates a wide range of analytical and preservation-oriented studies, extending from conservation planning and archival documentation (Biagini et al., 2016) to the assessment of seismic vulnerability (Rodrigues, et. Al, 2024) in historic structures.

A recent contribution with a distinct objective is presented by Vieira et al. (2024), who developed a semi-automated workflow integrating point cloud processing and a scan-to-BIM procedure aimed at capturing the complex morphology of the architectural ornaments of the Church of Nossa Senhora do Rosário. The proposed workflow encompasses a sequence of steps, including the acquisition of point cloud data, segmentation, mesh generation, mesh refinement, and the subsequent modeling of elements following BIM methodology.

Additional initiatives in the domain of modern heritage have also been documented, such as the study by Frazão (2022), which introduces a preventive and regular maintenance management system based on BIM technologies. In this framework, the integration of information into the digital building model allows for lifecycle monitoring of building components, including the scheduling of inspections and maintenance operations. The study selected the Palácio do Planalto as its case study, with the aim of generating actionable data to support the conservation and maintenance of this iconic modernist structure.

An additional application of the BIM methodology for structural analysis is demonstrated in the work of Gonçalves et al. (2022). The study aimed to compare two parallel models of the Church of “Nossa Senhora de Fátima,” alongside the results of their respective structural analyses. The first model was developed based on the building’s original structural documentation, whereas the second was constructed using precise surveying techniques commonly employed in historic BIM practices, including terrestrial laser scanning and aerophotogrammetry. The methodological approach centered on the automatic extraction of structural analysis results from the architectural representation of the building and its corresponding analytical abstraction.

2. Case Study – Metropolitan Cathedral of Brasilia

2.1 Architectural features

In 1958, Oscar Niemeyer articulated the design rationale behind the future Cathedral of Brasília as a pursuit of a compact architectural solution capable of preserving formal purity regardless of the vantage point. The adoption of a circular form, as he explained, not only fulfilled this criterion but also established a geometric, rational, and structurally coherent layout. The structural uprights were designed to define the façade in a rhythmically ascending sequence, while interspersed panels of neutral-colored refractory glass would ensure an atmosphere of contemplative calm within the interior, where the pulpit and choir were intended to emerge as focal elements through scale and plastic composition (Niemeyer, 1958).

Müller (2003) characterizes the cathedral's architectural and structural configuration as originating from a circular base recessed approximately three meters below the natural ground level. From this foundation, a series of juxtaposed parabolic pillars rise skyward, converging near the apex through a concrete slab, with glazed panels occupying the interstitial spaces between the columns (Figure 1). Niemeyer’s proposal for the Cathedral encapsulates a novel architectural experience that interweaves monumentality, symbolism, and social purpose. This intention is particularly evident in the entrance gallery, where the interplay between shadow and light, narrowness and openness, was meticulously orchestrated to heighten spatial perception.

Niemeyer (1978) emphasized that leading worshippers through a dimly lit corridor prior to entering the nave was a deliberate strategy aimed at intensifying the perceived luminosity of the sacred space through contrast. This spatial sequencing aligns with Le Corbusier's principle of architectural compression and release, wherein the constriction of the entry path amplifies the experience of light and spaciousness upon reaching the main interior (Niemeyer, 1978).

Figure 1 – The Metropolitan Cathedral of Brasilia.

2.2 Structural characteristics

The cornerstone of the Metropolitan Cathedral was laid on September 12, 1958. Designed by Oscar Niemeyer, the project was overseen by architect Carlos Magalhães and structural engineer Joaquim Cardoso. Its construction occurred in three distinct phases: the first from 1958 to 1960, the second from 1969 to 1970, and the third from 1976 to 1977. In the first phase, the cathedral began to take shape in 1959, when the main nave's structure was completed.

The structural conception of the cathedral is based on a circular floor plan with a diameter of 60 meters, defined by the arrangement of 16 columns. The system achieves self-equilibrium through the incorporation of two structural rings. The principal element is a tension ring situated at the base of the structure, ensuring lateral stability. A secondary compression ring, located 10 meters above the base, has a diameter of 6.8 meters and is responsible for absorbing the compressive forces transmitted by the columns. This upper ring features a cross-sectional width of 22 cm and a height of 90 cm. The lower portion of the structure includes multiple concentric rings spaced at 2-meter intervals, the main of which measures 200 cm in width and 50 cm in height. These rings are integrally connected by a cantilevered beam system extending toward the interior of the cathedral (Figure2).

The design of the hyperbolic columns stands out as particularly innovative and compelling for its time. The cross-section of each element varies continuously along its length, adopting a geometry reminiscent of a triangle—alternately hollow and solid. Construction was carried out using a lost formwork technique, resulting in a total of 22 distinct sections. Sections 01 through 04, as well as sections 18 through 22, are solid, whereas the intermediate segments are characterized by hollow sections. As indicated in certain design

drawings and reported by Pessoa (2002), the concrete's compressive strength was approximately 262.5 kgf/cm². Nonetheless, this value is regarded as ambitious given the technological and material limitations of the period. An examination of the original design documents reveals the presence of 70 longitudinal steel bars with a diameter of 1 inch within the hyperbolic columns at the cathedral's base. The reinforcing steel employed exhibits a yield strength of approximately 500 MPa. As the cross-sectional area of the columns increases, the number of reinforcing bars proportionally rises, exceeding 90 bars in the intermediate sections. Owing to the high reinforcement ratio, lap splicing could not be implemented (Figure 3).

Figure 2 – Detail of the lower tensile rings of the structural system.

Figure 3 – Detail of the 16th cross-section of the hyperbolic columns.

3. Methodology

3.1 Documentation

One of the earliest and most significant studies concerning the Cathedral of Brasília is the work of Pessoa (2002), which aimed to comprehensively characterize the monument's structural composition. The study addressed its historical context, architectural and structural design, the construction technologies employed, and the various interventions undertaken over time. It also provided a diagnostic assessment of the structure's condition at the time of research and proposed a structural maintenance program grounded in the methodology developed by the Graduate Program in Structures and Civil Construction at the University

of Brasília (UnB). Notably, this study contributed not only by fulfilling its stated objectives but also by enabling the digitization and adaptation of numerous printed design documents and structural calculations into a 2D computer-aided design (CAD) environment. Another highly relevant technical document is the *Inventory of the Metropolitan Cathedral of Brasília*, prepared under contract no. 03/2016 and as per the terms of public notice no. 01551.000149/2016-91. The document was developed by the team from Gema Arquitetura e Urbanismo, under the supervision of IPHAN-DF. Its purpose was to consolidate and systematize information concerning the modernist heritage embodied by the Cathedral, with particular emphasis on the work of Oscar Niemeyer.

Figure 4 – (a) Typical pillar of the Metropolitan Cathedral of Brasília, (b) Details of the lower ring of structure

The inventory serves as a foundation for actions related to oversight, preservation, and heritage education. The research methodology comprised comprehensive documentary and bibliographic reviews, analysis of architectural drawings, sketches, photographs, and records of all known interventions since the building's inception. The resulting document presents a detailed technical diagnosis of the structure, encompassing its landscaped areas, finish materials, integrated artworks, and furnishings, as well as the delineation of its surrounding context, with the goal of informing the ongoing management and physical conservation of the monument and its immediate environment. A considerable temporal gap exists between Pessoa's 2002 study and the development of the Inventory. Nevertheless, both documents constitute foundational references for understanding and preserving the Cathedral.

In the present study, digital modeling of the building was executed using Autodesk Revit (version 2022), complemented by algorithm developed in Dynamo for Revit plugin (version 3.3). Dynamo is a visual programming interface that facilitates the customization of workflows and the automation of tasks within the Building Information Modeling (BIM) environment. Owing to its open-source nature, the platform supports the integration of a wide array of modules and libraries, thereby enhancing its functionality. This modeling strategy enabled an accurate geometric representation of the structure, while also allowing for the integration of pertinent data throughout the building's life cycle—contributing substantively to the analysis, conservation, and informed management of this significant architectural heritage. As discussed by Pinti et. Al (2022), the integration of the Dynamo application with data management techniques establishes the necessary levels of data processing for the structured delivery of outputs. Through this documentation framework, users and stakeholders can access and extract data, technical reports, and supplementary information, including photographs, external sources, and related materials (Figure 5).

Figure 5 – Dynamo dataflow

Table 1 – The 21 cross-sections of hyperbolic columns

ID	Cross-Section	ID	Cross-Section	ID	Cross-Section
I					
II					
III					
IV					
V					

VI					
VII					

4. Results and discussion

Each structural cross-section was recreated in individual .RFA files, corresponding to parametric object families labeled according to the sectional numbering of the original design. The use of families within the Revit environment facilitates the systematic creation and management of elements, while maintaining the organization and integrity of the model data. A comprehensive list of the modeled cross-sections is provided in Table 1. Upon completion of the 22 sectional models, the algorithm implemented within the Dynamo for Revit environment follows the procedural steps outlined below: (1) Extraction of geometric linework from the associated .RFA file (figure 6); (2) Identification and selection of the outer contour of each cross-section; (3) Generation of surfaces from closed contours using the Surface.ByPatch function; (4) For both solid and perforated sections, the resulting surfaces served as the basis for volumetric modeling using the Solid.ByLoft command, which enables the lofting of sequential closed curves to generate three-dimensional solids representing the volumes between sectional intervals (Figure 7).

Figure 6 – Creation of BIM objects within Dynamo

In the BIM modeling environment (Autodesk Revit), other conventional structural elements — including the compression ring, lower ring beams, and circular slabs — were parameterized with varying dimensions. Given the absence of complex geometrical features, the modeling of these components was conducted in a more straightforward and efficient manner.

Figure 7 – Dynamo framework for creating solid from surface objects

The resulting solids were exported individually through the ExportToSAT node, enabling the production of geometry files compatible with various CAD and BIM platforms (Table 2). These discrete volumes were subsequently aggregated into a unified three-dimensional model, accurately composing each vertical element of the Cathedral.

Table 2– Some exported solids created with Dynamo

Solid Objects			

Figure 8 presents the complete 3D geometric model, incorporating various parametric objects associated with the structural elements of the Cathedral of Brasília. Other information from the model is the concrete volume as the compression ring comprises approximately 8.446 m³ of concrete while each hyperbolic column accounts for 35.122 m³. The circular roof slab contains 43.934 m³, underscoring its role in covering and stabilizing the upper structure. Additionally, the roof support columns or shell structures incorporate about 1.302 m³. It is noteworthy that several non-structural components integral to the site's historical heritage were not included in this case study, thereby leaving the model open for future expansions aimed at enriching and supporting the comprehensive documentation, analysis, and ongoing monitoring of the edifice. Among the prospective additions is the modeling of the stained-glass windows, which are supported by intricate three-dimensional steel truss structures affixed along the pillars.

Figure 8 – Parametric objects and BIM model developed

5. Conclusions

This study presents the development of a parametric model of the Cathedral of Brasília, with particular emphasis on the role of Building Information Modeling (BIM) in supporting the conservation of structures of historical and cultural value. Although the scope of this initial phase was restricted to structural elements, the model produced already enables critical structural analyses, including the assessment of parabolic ribs and the lower compression ring. The complex geometry of the parabolic elements was faithfully reconstructed through the implementation of algorithms developed using visual programming techniques, specifically within the Revit and Dynamo platforms. This modeling strategy ensured a high degree of geometric accuracy and methodological rigor, while simultaneously promoting interoperability across documentation, structural analysis, and heritage conservation workflows.

The objective of this work is to lay the foundation for a digital documentation repository that will facilitate the continuous enrichment of information related to the structure, encompassing geometric data, maintenance records, intervention histories, and preventive inspection reports — including the use of

advanced diagnostic techniques such as thermography. Nevertheless, challenges remain, particularly concerning the calibration of the model for advanced structural analyses and the integration of historical load data and records of past interventions, which will be addressed in future studies. Despite these limitations, the present work underscores the potential of parametric modeling combined with BIM as a strategic tool for the preservation, management, and sustainable conservation of built heritage.

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